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ABSTRACT

As a base for cultivating talents, the development of university campus sports culture has received extensive attention from all walks of life. This article analyzes the campus sports culture of American colleges and universities in a comprehensive way based on the theory of cultural quartation, and studies the reasons why American campus sports culture has been leading other countries for so many years, so as to figure out a practical path for the future development of campus sports in China. The reason why American university campus sports culture can achieve great success lies in its rich material culture, sound system culture, active spiritual culture and spontaneous behavioral culture. Therefore, the successful experience of the United States should be emulated, our own cultural characteristics made the best of. In the process of integrating sports-related culture into national culture, hopefully, the prejudice of underestimating the importance of sports held in traditional concepts can be rid of, the status of sports can be promoted, and the academic education for students with sport talent can be enhanced. Meanwhile, importance should be attached to fund-raising and the improvement of the system. With the above-mentioned measures, it is expected that the further development of campus sports culture in China can be promoted in a comprehensive way.

INTRODUCTION

University culture, which shoulders the mission of inheriting and innovating ideological culture, is an important driving force for the construction of socialist culture (Zhang, 2012). Among other things, the inheritance and innovation of university sports culture has received extensive attention from the society in recent years (Wang, Sun, 2016). Since 1985, in order to gain a systematic insight into the recent development and achievements of university sports culture in China, seven successive nationwide surveys have been conducted concerning university students' physique and health. It is a pity that although the data fluctuates in different ranges, the results shown are not satisfactory. Many people do not have the habit of doing sports, or sports are deemed as an occasional outdoor activity for entertainment. With regards to long-term, active, and purposeful sports activities, they seem to be what are exclusively for talented P.E. students and professional athletes. Although some universities have the records of winning Olympic or National Games championships, most of these honorees are professional athletes hired and they are just nominal members in the university, rather than students who receive exclusive teaching and training in the university (Sun, 2017). On the contrary, American universities have indeed cultivated many Olympic champions. Among the previous Olympic delegations of the United States, the proportion of college students has reached 70%, who have won the Olympic gold medals for the United States many times (Weike, 2014). Faced with such a huge gap, that is why we have to thoroughly analyze the American university campus culture and learn from its success.

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The Advanced Campus Sports Culture of American Universities

Campus sports culture refers to the culture within the school, created by the teachers and students of the school in the course of specific practice. Based on its manifestation, it falls into two parts: explicit culture and implicit culture. At the content level, it comprises material culture, institutional culture, spiritual culture and behavioral culture.

The Rich Material Culture

The physical material of the university is the explicit culture of the campus, including all the funds, sports equipment, stadiums (gymnasiums) and other facilities needed in all sports activities. Sports material culture, a prerequisite for the development of sports culture, provides material conditions for the development of sports culture, and makes the promotion and advancement of sports possible.

Multi-Channel Funding Sources

In the United States, be it a public university or a private one, in most cases, the operating funds should be raised by the university herself. Even for the most prestigious universities like University of Virginia and University of California, Berkeley, government funding only accounts for 10% of all the expenses needed, which impels universities to expand their funding channels. As a result, student tuition and related donations and funding have become their main source of income. In order to obtain sufficient funds, they must work hard to procure donations from all sides. Philanthropy channel alone may not be enough to fill such a huge fund gap. As a matter of fact, in America, competitive sports enjoys the same popularity as academic endeavors. The experience from Clemson University demonstrates to us that if a university can cultivate excellent athletes, a direct effect is more enrollments for the school. After winning the rugby championship, Clemson received 17% more applications for admission compared with previous year (Scripps Howard News Service, 2001). Major colleges and universities actively participate in the annual league matches held by the National Collegiate Athletic Association, NCAA[†]. Once excellent results are achieved in the competition, the resultant economic benefits can be a sufficient source of material assurance for the university. The NCAA's 2015 Annual University Financial Report shows that 50 colleges and universities amassed up to 304 million revenues by means of ticket-selling, TV shows, website broadcasts, financial support from sponsors and advertisements. What matters most is that these huge revenues will be distributed to colleges and universities in a certain proportion, and colleges and universities will then invest this part of the proceeds into the training and cultivation of athletic teams. In addition to these huge incomes, NCAA will offer insurance premiums, scholarships, and internship programs to student athletes participating in the National Championship every year as well (The NCAA Budget, 2013). NCAA has enabled the formation of a trinity consisted of academics, physical education, and business in the member schools of the association. Meanwhile, the series of leagues held by NCAA condensed the alma mater complex and sense of honor of the alumni of American colleges and universities, which also brings considerable alumni donations. Sufficient multi-channel sports funding sources have laid a material foundation for the development of campus sports culture.

High-Standard Sports Facilities

Modern stadiums for college students that meet international standards have made great contributions to American campus sports culture. These gymnasiums are built based on the concept of multi-function, composite, integration and internationalization, and the utilization rate is extremely high. The Los Angeles Memorial Gymnasium, built in 1923 and meeting the Olympic standard in size, is fully equipped and magnificent, which can accommodate 92,604 spectators at the same time. It can not

[†]① NCAA is a non-profit social organization initiated by the joint efforts of American universities and colleges, composed of all members, employees and college athletes who are willing to abide by the charter of the association. NCAA has always been operated on the core development concept- Education First and Sports Serving for Education. With commitments to devoting itself to the well-being and lifelong-success of college student athletes, for the time being, more than 1,000 universities in the United States have joined the NCAA, including not only the world's top universities such as Harvard University and Yale University, but also many small colleges and community colleges.

only host all large-scale cultural and sports activities of the school, but also enables the University of Southern California to have won numerous awards in sports competitions at home and abroad. In addition to such large stadiums, small stadiums and gyms can be found everywhere as well. These gymnasiums offer almost everything needed and can not only carry out traditional sports games, but also support emerging sports activities such as basketball, badminton, karate, judo and so on, to name just a few, all of which can be part of campus sports culture. With the support of multi-functional and high-standard sports facilities, students in colleges and universities can do their preferable exercise any time they feel like to. All in all, the multifunctional gymnasiums have to a large degree met the needs of American college students for extracurricular sports activities and sports club activities by offering the needed venues and facilities, which serves as material assurance for the development of competitive sports in American universities.

A Sound Institutional Culture

Sports system culture comprises sports rules and regulations along with sports organizations, which is considered the superstructure of the sports industry and which can directly impact the development of sports culture. The prosperity of American college sports culture is inseparable from its excellent institutional culture.

A All-Around Three-Level Management System

A well-developed organization can guarantee the routine operation of an organization. Currently, American college athletic sports are being carried out under a three-level management system comprising NACC, regional school alliances, and school management, among which, NACC is the first-level management, responsible for supervising the national university competitive sports; the alliances formed by schools in various regions is the second-level management, shouldering the responsibility of presiding over the sports work in line with the local characteristic culture; the competitive sports management organizations established by each university in its own context occupy the third level, which is also the most basic layer. However, due to the independence and target-orientation of the third level management, it works best to promote the development of the school's campus sports culture according to the status quo and needs of the university. The interlocking and close integration of the three-level management system is the key to the successful development of competitive sports in American universities. In the three-level management system, the Athletic Departments at the third level play a most basic role. In China, the primary responsibility of PE departments in universities is to offer PE courses and carry out physical testing. However, the PE Departments in the United States are mainly responsible for carrying out college sports training and competition, which is almost essentially different from the obligation assumed by PE Departments in China. In some Division I[‡] universities, the Competitive Sports Department is a huge organization, similar to professional sports associations or professional clubs, covering departments of administrative management, human resources, information and media, marketing and tickets, venues and facilities so on, so forth. These departments coordinate with one another to deal with various matters such as allocating venues, setting open and close time for gyms, and scheduling competitions so that campus sports can be carried out in an orderly manner.

Sports and Education, Two In One

The superiority of the educational system of American universities is also reflected in enrollment, teaching, training and other aspects. Different from the training scheme exclusively aiming to cultivate students specializing in sports, American universities adhere to the approach of Sports and Education, Two in One, focusing on the organic integration of the two (Zhuo, Sun & Liu, 2017). Outstanding competitive sports competence is not the only criterion for selecting college athletes, and even Olympic champions can not enjoy any privilege in the entrance examination. Surprisingly, despite of

[‡] These universities and colleges with official NCAA membership constitute three divisions, namely, Division I, Division II and Division III. On a yearly basis, the official members of the three divisions must meet the requirements designated for the divisions they are in, and participate in the sports competitions at their respective division level.

such high requirements for athletes' academic study and athletic competition, universities still stipulates that college athletes can only train for an average of 2 hours a day. In other words, even athletes should not place too much emphasis on sports competitions and neglect their academic study, which differs from the "half for academic study -half for training" scheme to ensure sufficient training time in China. Furthermore, in order to guarantee that college student athletes possess a consistent and complete knowledge system, if they fail to attend some academic sessions due to training or matches, the university will require professors to make up for the missing lectures for them (Feng ,2014). In order to ensure its proper implementation, universities will also enforce disciplinary measures to disallow those who fail in academic tests to participate in training and competitions. In addition to the dual requirements for students, namely, athlete students should do well both in their academic studies and athletic performances, universities in America have framed detailed and strict assessment criteria and related responsibility to be fulfilled for and by coaches. The American NCAA Coaching Code stipulates that the head coaches coaching in American college sports teams must possess NCAA professional certification, and must receive regular training and assessment every year. The numerous requirements not only provide quality assurance for the academic education of college student athletes, but also provide policy guarantee for the sustainable development of physical education in American universities.

Positive Spiritual Culture

Sports spiritual culture includes sports ideology and sports values, and is the core of campus sports culture. Sports ideology is an important guiding ideology of the management administrative staff's for sports education in the sports industry. The American sports ideology holds the view that sports should aim to promote the development of students in the following four aspects: physical, cognitive, social and emotional. It should focus on cultivating students' interest in sports and enable students to establish lifelong exercise habits. While sports values refer to the society's value orientation towards sports. American universities regard school honor and personal honor as the first value of sports, and physical exercise and spiritual cultivation as the "hidden value". This sense of honor is deeply rooted in the hearts of the American people, gradually making sports a sunny, healthy and glorious activity. On American campuses, be it early in the morning or late at night, college students can be seen everywhere on the playground, in the arena, and in the gym. They all firmly believe that no matter what career they will be engaged in in the future, as long as they want to conquer the world, a strong will and a strong body will be a must. In other words, sports has become a part of their lives and is considered an essential activity for a happy life. This kind of spirit has been passed down from generation to generation in the United States. Most families pay special attention to the knowledge their children have learned in sports and have focused on shaping their children's character through continuous and lasting sports exercises from childhood on.

Spontaneous Behavioral Culture

Behavioral culture refers to the activities in which people instinctively respond to certain internal or external stimuli and the purposeful activities that people consciously carry out for certain needs. Sports behavioral culture is the source of motivation for the construction of sports culture in American universities. Physical education, extracurricular sports activities and sports competitions are the driving force for the development of university sports culture and serve as the main body for the construction of university sports culture (Wang, Sun, 2016).

Sports Outweighing PE in American Universities

Unlike China, in many world-class universities, there are no exclusive sports colleges or departments. Although compulsory physical education courses are offered in them, it is more on the side of integrating the Olympic spirit into students' daily activities and competitions. What they attach importance to is not a physical education that is systematically-organized or assumes various forms with nothing to distinguish itself, but a spontaneous, life-based voluntary exercise. In American universities, Sports carries more weight than Physical Education. However, American colleges and universities that do not offer compulsory physical education courses do not neglect the importance of sports for students. They adopt a non-compulsory physical education scheme to allow students more

freedom to choose what they like. On the one hand, American colleges and universities cultivate students' interest in sports gradually and bit by bit through promoting and disseminating the spirit of competitive sports. On the other hand, although universities do not require students to do exercise, they actively encourage students to participate in sports clubs and intramural competitions and provide students with excellent sports facilities. For most college students who are frequenters to gymnasiums, the above-mentioned measures are sufficient for them to maintain a lifestyle featuring physical exercises.

Multi-Carriers of Promoting Athletic Contest Elements

Sports logos, team theme songs, and iconic sports figures are all indispensable sports elements in athletic contests. For Chinese visiting scholars in the United States, the all-year-round NCAA league matches, hats, T-shirts, and hoodies with school logos will never fail to impress them concerning the campus sports culture of American universities. In all those non-stop leagues, the fans, which are partly made up of university alumni, faithfully follow every game, and even the principal will be among the spectators to cheer the players and present awards. When the school team leave for the regional or national league, a seeing-off party will be held by the university to boost the morale of the team. In addition, university official website also posts real-time news of the games, team records, seasonal game schedule, daily report, admission information, and so on. These efforts have paid off immensely, compared with the alumni meetings spontaneously organized by universities in China. The tradition of watching sports games can condense the friendship of generations of alumni in a more solid way, which can in turn generate huge donations and sponsorship.

Enlightenment to Universities in China on Campus Sports Culture

As a Chinese old saying goes, the stones from other hills can be used to polish gems. American university campus sports culture sets a successful example for the universities in our country. Their success lies in the following four aspects: material, system, spirit and behavior. A careful comparison with the status quo of campus sports culture in China shows that we can learn from the experience of the United States in four ways: fund-raising, facility construction, management system, teaching system, sports values and sports behavior.

Multi-Channel to Raise Sports Funds

Unlike in China, where university sports funding solely relies on financial grant from the government, in the U.S. the fund-raising mode assumes a diversified model (Jiang, 2006) featuring self-financing as the major income source while government grant a supplement, which provides sufficient economic assurance and support for university sports and competitive sports. However, in addition to the single source of funding for universities in China, the other obstacle to the development of PE refers to the insufficiency of university sports funding, which accounts for less than 2% of university funding for academic education (data quoted from the "The Goals and Countermeasures for the Sports Material Conditions Development of Chinese Schools"). Except for sports colleges, it is difficult for other types of colleges and universities to introduce more funds for campus sports construction. As a result, with the funding problem, an imminent consequence is the stagnation in the quality and number of sports facilities, and it seems an unreachable dream to be an equal with American universities in this aspect. To solve this problem, China should put more efforts into the commercialization of university sports events, look into market needs and meet these needs, integrating resources, and pinpointing university responsibility, so as to secure sufficient funds for the development of campus sports culture.

To Establish a Sound Sports System

The long-term separation of the education system from the sports system in China has led to a misunderstanding with regards to the cultivation of high-quality athletes in universities: due to the foregrounding of athletic students' identity as athletes, the role of academic classes which have nothing to do with sports competitions is overshadowed by the championship medals. With this kind of wrong perception, there have even emerged phenomena like awarding credits to athletic students according to the scores they get in sports competitions, and adding certain credits to their academic profile based on the athletic grading they get when admitted to the university in order to meet the

total credits requirement for high-quality athletes. The imminent consequence of the normalization of this kind of behavior is student athletes' relatively poor academic performance in Chinese universities. To address this problem, we should establish a complete talent selection and management system across the country, learn from the US model, namely, Sports and Education, Two in One, emphasize the significance of academic studies for sports athletes and student athletes with sport talent, so that sports athletes can gain high level competence in sports.

To Cultivate Emerging Campus Sports Spiritual Culture

It is known that the inherent traditional culture of each country will have a subtle impact on the overall development of her society. In our country, the slow development of campus sports culture can be to a large degree attributed to the influence of our traditional culture. With Confucian culture impact, the fundamental purpose of doing sports in China is to keep fit and build up strength. Despite the fact that there remained in the Shi Culture, which can be dated far back to the pre-Qin period, a trace of martial arts spirit, this acknowledgement and worship for warriors gradually faded off in the course of history after the Han Dynasty, with the permeation of Confucian culture. In the Tang Dynasty, military attaches were regarded insignificant and inferior, and in the Song Dynasty started the tradition of civil officials governing the country after the transfer of military power from the military officials to the Emperor Zhao Kuangyin in the early Song Dynasty. Consequentially, the weakening of martial arts spirit and physical education renders PE a trivial course. Up to this day, the essence of sports values in China is still characterized by the concept that the significance of sports lies in its body strengthening function and glory-winning effect. Under the guidance of these values, the number of people who simply do sports for nothing has been greatly reduced. In addition, contemporary students are struggling to cope with complicated academic courses and assessments, and the time allocated for sports has been immensely cut down. What's worse, occasionally PE classes will be replaced by academic sessions. There are also some students who are limited by their inherent thinking and hold the view that sports have nothing to do with them, but that it is exclusively for athletes. In Chinese universities, unless there are chances for students to participate in major sports competitions, one even with excellent sports talent and outstanding sports skills will not be regarded as an Athlete. If this misconception cannot be rectified timely, the prospects for the development of campus sports competitions will only become more worrying. In the United States, anyone who is good at a certain sport and has participated in competitions of any size will be included in the ranks of "athletes" and become a sought-after superstar in colleges and universities, enjoying the heroic privileges. The absence of the atmosphere for or a weak emphasis on sports competitions both are not conducive to the overall development of students (Wang, Nie & Li, 2019). Acknowledging the importance of sports is an indispensable factor in promoting the development of sports culture and cultivating a wholesome and diverse sportsmanship culture is what China should do.

To Establish a Rich Sports Behavioral Culture

The cultural atmosphere of campus sports competition in America is far greater than that of our country. On the one hand, the efforts put forward by universities in the two countries to promote campus competition culture can not be juxtaposed. On the other hand, Chinese students' awareness of participating in sports competitions is far less than that of American students, which is caused by our country's physical education teaching approach. Physical education in our country pays more attention to the comprehensiveness of the content of teaching materials. Although this original intention aims to help students know more about the types of sports, the practice has deviated from the motive and it has resulted in cultivating a bunch of jack-of-all-trades. In addition, with poor sports facilities in communities, students are short of the facilities and venues to exercise outside the school. Most of the time, they can only exercise themselves in school sports activities, which largely reduces their voluntariness to engage in physical activities. Furthermore, for those who are sports fanatics, their sudden lack of interest in PE classes can be accounted for by the monotonous way of teaching, which is simply syllabus-based and in which only technical PE skills are taught. PE courses can not offer students chance to Exert What They Have Learned, and meanwhile it is difficult for schools to provide students with a competition platform to show their sports competence. In response to these

problems, universities at all levels should take strong measures to implement the resolutions reached, change educational concepts, and organize more sports competitions so that students have access to more flexible ways of carrying out sports activities along with the platforms to exert their sports skills. Only by doing so can the sports behavioral culture be promoted, students' constitution strengthened, sports competition culture developed.

Conclusion

Students' overall development and campus sports culture complement each other. For students to be mentally and physically wholesome, the influence of campus sports culture plays a major role, and the further development of it also depends on the support from students. Compared with American universities, the obstacles impeding the construction of sports culture in Chinese universities are their lack of sufficient funding sources, the negative influence received from traditional cultural ideas, and the imperfect existing system. As for the so-called rejuvenation scheme, namely, to invigorate the country through education, the development and perfection of university campus sports culture is the main force in making this dream come true by building a leading sports nation. We should draw on the experience of the United States in established itself a leading sports nation, by way of promoting the marketization of campus sports, expanding funding sources, building high-quality sports venues, focusing on athletes' academic literacy, establishing new campus sports concepts, and providing students with diverse opportunities for exerting their sports competence, the campus sports culture in our country can be upgraded to a new height.

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